

John Wustman

Special Thanks

Dr. David Atwater
Bernie Hanus Freeman
Rachel Jensen
Janet Manning
Cheryl Newcomb
Dr. James Scott
Ruth Stolfus
Jerry Tessin
Classic Events
Levis Faculty Center
Todd Waldecker

a c e l e b r a t i o n
7 0 y e a r s

Sunday
December 17, 2000
3:00 pm
Smith Recital Hall
University of Illinois

Program

- Adelaide* Beethoven (1770-1827)
John Bellemor, tenor ('94)
Jessica Paul, pianist ('96)
- Schöne Wiege* Schumann (1810-1856)
Mondnacht Mary Ann Hart, mezzo-soprano ('76)
Dulip Highfill, pianist ('75)
- De miei bollenti spiriti* from *La Traviata* Verdi (1813-1901)
David S. Mannell, tenor ('90)
Susan S. Ashbaker
- The Bird of the Wilderness* ~~Horsman~~ (1873-1918)
Susan Dunn, soprano
Rachel Jensen, pianist (current student)
- Von ewiger Liebe* Brahms (1833-1897)
William Thomas, baritone ('93)
Jessica Paul, pianist ('96)
- Wiegenlied* Spohr (1784-1859)
Rebekah Demarco, soprano ('91)
Anno Thurmond, clarinet ('90)
Paul Thurmond, pianist ('92)
- Rastlose Liebe* Schubert (1828-1897)
Linda Thorne, soprano ('71)
Julie Gunn, pianist ('00)
- Après un Rêve* Faure (1845-1924)
Boyd Mackus, baritone ('77)
Julie Gunn, pianist ('00)
- Ganymed* Schubert (1897-1828)
Sue Arnold, mezzo-soprano ('75)
Eric Malson, pianist (Indiana University)
- Al prologo from Pagliacci* ~~Leoncavallo~~
Infelice from "ERNANI" Verdi (1858-1919)
Eric Halverson
Thomas H. Rollet, baritone
Felena Kurdina, pianist ('85)
- Il vecchietto cerca moglie* Rossini (1792-1868)
from *Il Barbiere di Siviglia*
Katharine DeBoer, soprano ('93)
Brian Garman, pianist
- Befreit* Strauss (1864-1949)
Monica Gerbe, soprano
Carol Goff, pianist ('00)
- Im Frühling* Schubert (1897-1828)
Ralph Klapis, baritone
Joseph Bogner, pianist ('00)
- Lebewohl* Welf (1860-1903)
Lucinda Sloan, soprano ('85)
Felena Kurdina, pianist ('85)
- Der zürnende Barde* Schubert (1828-1897)
Jeffrey Foote, baritone ('75)
Julie Gunn, pianist ('00)
- Zueignung* Strauss (1864-1949)
Julie Simson, mezzo-soprano ('81)
Paul Thurmond, pianist ('92)
- Il Pastor* Pizzetti (1880-1968)
Lucas Cannon, tenor (current student)
Rachel Jensen, pianist (current student)
- Io sono l'umile ancella* from *Adriana Lecouvreur* Filar (1866-1950)
Alice Copper, soprano ('77)
Jeffrey Peterson, pianist (current student)
- Du bist die Ruh* Schubert (1828-1897)
Jane Jennings, soprano ('93)
Eric Malson, pianist (Indiana University)
- Aleko's Aria from Aleko* Rachmaninoff (1873-1943)
Eric Halverson, baritone ('76)
Felena Kurdina, pianist ('85)

Interval